

Documentation for D5.2 ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground

Funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research SGR
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SER

UK Research
and Innovation

Grant Agreement Number	101135916	Acronym	ELOQUENCE
Full Title	Multilingual and Cross-cultural interactions for context-aware, and bias controlled dialogue systems for safety-critical applications		
Project Start Date	01/01/2024	Duration	36 months
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Project URL	ELOQUENCEai.eu , Interactive Playground		
Deliverable	D5.2 ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground		
Work Package	WP5 – Piloting		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/06/2025	Actual 27/06/2025
Type	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype		
Lead Beneficiary	OM		
Author(s)/ Organisation(s)	CNR, TID, OM		
Contributor(s)	Giuseppe Caggianese, Pietro Neroni (CNR) Jordi Luque, Aleix Sant (TID) Themos Stafylakis, Vojtech Hudecek, Christos Ferles (OM)		
Abstract			

Document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	27/05/2025		ToC	CNR, OM
1.0	07/06/2025		Main Document	OM, CNR
1.1	20/06/2025		1st Review	CNR, TID
1.2	24/06/2025		2nd Review	OM, CNR
1.3	27/06/2025		3rd Review	OM, CNR, TID

Dissemination level

PU – Public, fully open, e.g., web	✓
SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

ELOQUENCE Consortium

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Role*
1	TELEFONICA INNOVACION DIGITAL SL	TID	ES	COO
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR	IT	BEN
3	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC	ES	BEN
4	FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER	FBK	IT	BEN
5	UNIVERZITET U NOVOM SADU FAKULTET TEHNICKIH NAUKA	UNS	RS	BEN
6	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE	EUI	IT	BEN (IO)
7	VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V BRNE	BUT	CZ	BEN
8	PRIVANOVA SAS	PN	FR	BEN
9	INOSENS DOO NOVI SAD	INO	RS	BEN
10	TRANSFORMATION LIGHTHOUSE, POSLOVNO SVETOVANJE, D.O.O.	TL	SI	BEN
11	GRANTXPRT CONSULTING LIMITED	GX	CY	BEN
12	OMILIA MONOPROSOPI ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS PAROXIS PLIROFORIKON, TILEPIKOINONIAKON KAI FONITIKON YPIRESION KAI SYSTIMATON	OM	EL	BEN
13	SYNELIXIS LYSEIS PLIROFORIKIS AUTOMATISMOU & TILEPIKOINONION ANONIMI ETAIRIA	SYN	EL	BEN
14	FONDATION DE L'INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE IDIAP	IDIAP	CH	AP
15	BRUNEL UNIVERSITY LONDON	BUL	UK	AP
16	UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX	UESSEX	UK	AP

Role: COO-Coordinator; BEN-Beneficiary; AE-Affiliated Entity; AP-Associated Partner

QUALITY OF INFORMATION - DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

© ELOQUENCE Consortium, 2024.

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2	INTRODUCTION.....	9
2.1	IP RELATION WITH PILOTS	10
3	USER MANUAL.....	14
3.1	UI OVERVIEW.....	14
3.1.1	<i>Tabs and Layout</i>	14
3.1.2	<i>Concept of Tasks</i>	16
3.2	VECTOR STORES AND RETRIEVAL-AUGMENTED GENERATION (RAG).....	17
3.2.1	<i>What is RAG?</i>	17
3.2.2	<i>Ingestion of Documents</i>	17
3.2.3	<i>Private vs. Public Vector Stores</i>	22
3.3	SERVED MODELS	23
3.3.1	<i>LLMs</i>	23
3.3.2	<i>Audio Models</i>	24
3.3.3	<i>Embedding models</i>	25
3.4	USER FEEDBACK COLLECTION.....	25
3.5	ADVANCED FUNCTIONALITY	26
3.5.1	<i>System Prompts</i>	26
3.5.2	<i>Storing Conversation Sessions</i>	26
3.5.3	<i>Batch Data Processing</i>	26
4	ARCHITECTURE AND TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION.....	28
4.1	ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW.....	28
4.1.1	<i>Containerization</i>	28
4.1.2	<i>Audio Processing</i>	29
4.1.3	<i>Vector Store Integration</i>	29
4.2	SYSTEM CONFIGURATION	29
4.2.1	<i>Task configs</i>	29
4.2.2	<i>Retrievers</i>	30
4.2.3	<i>User Configuration</i>	30
4.3	RUNNING THE INSTANCE.....	30
4.3.1	<i>Run the IP</i>	30
4.3.2	<i>Run the local Vector Store</i>	31
4.4	USED SOFTWARE	31
5	FUTURE WORK.....	33
5.1	PLANNED FEATURES/MODULES.....	33
6	APPENDIX A: API REFERENCES	34

List of figures

Figure 1. The main playground tab	15
Figure 2. The ingestion tab.....	16
Figure 3. The feedback tab.....	16
Figure 4. Details of the ingestion process	18
Figure 5. Choosing the index name	18
Figure 6. Ingestion process chunking configuration.....	19
Figure 7. Selecting a vector store.....	20
Figure 8. Selecting a vector store.....	20
Figure 9. Uploading documents for ingestion	21
Figure 10. Comparison of public vs private vector store setup	22
Figure 11. Data flow of retrieval when using the public vector store.....	22
Figure 12. The data flow of retrieval in the private setup	23
Figure 13. Display of the user feedback.....	25
Figure 14. Structure of the downloaded history snapshot	26
Figure 15. Overall architecture of the Interactive Playground system.....	28

List of tables

Table 1. Summary of pilot-related KRs	13
---	----

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

LLM	Large Language Model
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
IP	Interactive Playground

1 Executive Summary

The document presents the **Interactive Playground (IP)** and constitutes supporting documentation for the D5.2. The main deliverable is a DEM—Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, meaning that the primary objective is the release of the IP.

The D5.2 release includes the following materials:

IP deployment publicly available at <https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/>

- source code publicly available through the Eloquence project GitHub: <https://github.com/ELOQUENCEAI/eloquence-interactive-playground>
- IP supporting documentation: This document presents the User Manual, the Architecture Design and the API references in the annex.

In relation to the first point, to preserve the system from an uncontrollable number of accesses, the IP is actually publicly released but protected by credentials. At the moment of the release of this document, it is not possible for an external user to create an account, but people interested can contact the OM partner, who will validate the requests. Moreover, since this document will be publicly available too, a set of credentials will be shared with the PO of the ELOQUENCE project to ensure access to project reviewers.

The **IP** is the central experimentation and demonstration environment of the ELOQUENCE project. It brings together the multilingual and multimodal language technologies developed across all project Work Packages, enabling real-time validation, iterative testing, and stakeholder engagement within the project's use-case pilots. Furthermore, the IP represents the core component that facilitates the implementation of the project's pilots supporting the achievement of **KR16**, **KR17**, and **KR18**. The technologies developed will be applied to the pilot scenarios to demonstrate and validate the effectiveness of the proposed virtual agents in real-world applications. The different pilots can be summarized as: **Pilot 1** implements privacy-preserving federated learning for smart home virtual assistants; **Pilot 2** develops social context-aware bias detection systems for sensitive applications like career counselling; **Pilot 3** creates retrieval-augmented customer service agents capable of cross-industry deployment; and **Pilot 4** establishes AI-powered healthcare call centre supervision systems for care support. Overall, via its dual role (as a technical integration hub and as a researcher/user engagement tool), it serves the project's objectives of establishing conversational AI frameworks and demonstrating technology capabilities across diverse application scenarios.

The IP offers a dynamic and modular platform where partners can interact with and evaluate a range of Large Language Models (LLMs), dialog components and supporting tools. Each pilot instance of the IP is fully contextualised; configured with domain-specific data, dialog flows and user interaction patterns tailored to its objectives.

Operating on the BSC's cloud-based High-Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure, the IP supports large-scale, privacy-preserving deployments.

The organization of the rest of the document is as follows:

Motivation and Use Cases establishes the foundational rationale for the Interactive Playground, outlining how it addresses critical needs in conversational AI development and validation. **Related Pilots** provides context for how the platform integrates with and supports the four ELOQUENCE pilots.

UI Overview presents the platform's intuitive interface design, featuring a tab-based layout and workflow system that enables seamless navigation between different functionalities. **Vector Stores and RAG** details the Retrieval-Augmented Generation capabilities, including comprehensive document ingestion processes with configurable

chunking, vector store selection and embedder options, alongside private vs. public storage configurations for enhanced data security. **Served Models** showcases the platform's AI model support, including advanced LLMs (GPT-3.5, Salamandra, OLMo 2, EuroLLM-9B), audio processing models (Qwen2-Audio), and specialized embedding models for diverse application requirements. **User Feedback Collection** and **Advanced Functionality** demonstrate the platform's feedback gathering mechanisms, system prompt customization, conversation session management and batch processing capabilities.

Architecture Overview presents the platform's containerized infrastructure featuring specialized components including the frontend interface, retriever services, hosted model management and dialogue manager, complemented by advanced audio processing and vector store integration capabilities. **System Configuration** details the flexible configuration framework encompassing task-specific settings, retriever configurations, and user customization options. **Running the Instance** and **Used Software** sections provide comprehensive deployment guidance and document the platform's technology stack, including Docker containerization, Gradio interface framework, LanceDB vector storage, FastAPI backend services and vLLM model serving infrastructure.

Last, **Future Work** contains an indicative series of extensions/enhancements of the platform that will follow a continuous R&D cycle extending beyond the limits of Task 5.3.

The comprehensive **API Reference** provides detailed specifications for eight core endpoints that enable programmatic interaction with the platform. Key functionalities include real-time LLM querying (`/query`), batch processing capabilities (`/batch_query`), document ingestion and indexing (`/ingest`), similarity-based document retrieval (`/retrieval`), feedback collection (`/feedback`) and system resource discovery endpoints (`/list_vs`, `/list_llms`, `/list_embedders`). Each endpoint includes complete parameter specifications and request/response examples for seamless development workflows.

2 Introduction

The **Interactive Playground (IP)** is a critical component of the ELOQUENCE ecosystem, designed to bridge the gap between advanced language technologies and their real-world applications across multiple domains. Its primary role is to provide a unified, user-accessible environment where stakeholders—researchers, developers, domain experts, and end-users—can interact with the ELOQUENCE models in a hands-on and iterative manner.

The need for such component stems from the complex nature of the project's goals: validating large, multilingual and multimodal language models across varied use cases, while ensuring ethical compliance, technological adaptability and societal robustness. The IP addresses these needs by enabling interactive access to LLMs and dialog systems, both through a user-friendly web interface and a programmatic REST API, ensuring flexibility for both technical and non-technical users.

The IP serves not merely as a testing ground, but as a collaborative and extensible framework designed to evolve in step with the advancing technologies and insights emerging from ELOQUENCE. The comprehensive range of macroscopic as well as specific uses, applications and functionalities of the IP can be organized into six main pillars:

1. PRE-DEPLOYMENT TESTING

- **Safe Testing Environment:** Provide a controlled space to test complex LLM systems before real-world deployment
- **Algorithm Validation:** Verify that core LLM algorithms (federated learning, bias detection, information retrieval, urgency assessment) function correctly
- **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Experimentation:** Test pipelines, integrating enterprise or domain-specific knowledge
- **Performance Benchmarking:** Establish baseline performance metrics across different domains and use cases
- **Audio Model Analysis:** Access and test such models in realistic conversational scenarios
- **System Integration Testing:** Ensure multiple LLM components work together seamlessly

2. STAKEHOLDER DEMONSTRATION

- **Interactive Technology Showcase:** Allow partners, users and decision-makers to experience the respective LLM capabilities
- **Proof-of-Concept Demonstrations:** Provide tangible examples of how advanced LLM technologies work in practice
- **Trust Building:** Enable stakeholders to interact with developed LLMs and evaluate them before committing to deployment
- **Technology Transfer:** Bridge the gap between research developments and practical applications

3. CUSTOMIZATION & ADAPTATION PLATFORM

- **Domain-Specific Configuration:** Adapt LLM systems for different industries, contexts and organizational needs
- **Data Integration Testing:** Validate how LLM systems perform with partner-specific datasets and documents
- **Use Case Personalization:** Customize LLM behavior, dialogue flows and responses for specific applications
- **Vector Store Management:** Ensure that embeddings used for retrieval remain up-to-date, efficient and tailored to specific use-case requirements

4. ITERATIVE DEVELOPMENT & REFINEMENT

- **Rapid Prototyping:** Enable quick testing and iteration of LLM system modifications

- **Real-Time Performance Monitoring:** Observe system behavior and identify areas for improvement
- **Feedback-Driven Development:** Submit feedback directly on model outputs, enabling the collection of qualitative and quantitative insights for iterative improvement
- **Continuous Quality Assurance:** Ongoing validation of LLM system accuracy, safety and appropriateness

5. MULTI-STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION

- **Professional User Testing:** Provide specialized testing environments for domain experts (healthcare professionals, counselors, customer service managers)
- **Cross-Functional Feedback Collection:** Gather insights from technical developers, end-users and business stakeholders
- **Knowledge Sharing Platform:** Facilitate collaboration between different pilot teams and research groups

6. RISK MITIGATION & SAFETY VALIDATION

- **Privacy Protection Testing:** Ensure LLM systems maintain data privacy and security standards
- **Bias Detection & Mitigation:** Identify and address potential biases in LLM responses across different demographic groups
- **Response Controls:** Prompt and interrogate models in real time to evaluate their linguistic, emotional and contextual responses
- **Accuracy Verification:** Prevent dissemination of incorrect information or LLM hallucinations

2.1 IP relation with Pilots

The IP serves as a comprehensive testing and development platform that enables hands-on user experience with pilot technologies while facilitating direct communication between users and developers. This creates an iterative feedback loop that continuously guides refinement and adjustment of each respective pilot.

Pilot 1: “Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralized training in smart homes” (D5.1, subsection 2.1)

The privacy-preserving language model pilot addresses the critical challenge of developing AI models that can benefit from global knowledge while maintaining strict privacy standards in domestic environments. This innovative approach leverages Federated Learning (FL) to enable multiple clients to collaboratively train language models and automatic speech recognition systems without directly sharing sensitive data. Rather than transmitting raw user-s data to centralized servers, the FL framework shares, e.g. only model parameters from local devices to a central aggregation server, ensuring that client-specific information remains private while still allowing individual models to benefit from collective learning insights. This methodology enables personalization and domain adaptation of AI models across heterogeneous computing environments, from end-user devices to edge nodes and cloud platforms.

While the FL-training and orchestration is implemented and accessible by the clients through a CLI interface, the Pilot 1 will integrate essential technologies including keyword spotting for voice activation, automatic speech recognition, speaker diarization, and LLMs to create a comprehensive virtual assistant agent that can operate effectively within simulated domestic environments. For doing so, the IP plays the key role of agent orchestrator for the critical testing and validation environment of the Pilot 1's FL models, allowing stakeholders to test the virtual assistant capabilities in a simulated smart home environment. The IP enables comprehensive testing of the virtual assistant's understanding capabilities on unstructured dialogues occurring in a household. Researchers can use the pilot to simulate various household scenarios, test speech capabilities and validate that FL models do not leak sensitive personal data. Additionally, the IP serves as both as a demonstration platform and a feedback collection tool for stakeholders, enabling potential users and partners to interact with smart home virtual assistants and experience the natural language understanding and privacy-preserving capabilities firsthand. This enables the pilot's team to gather crucial user feedback on usability expectations, privacy concerns and system performance while refining the federated learning approach.

Pilot 2: “Social context-aware language model detecting biases” (D5.1, subsection 2.2)

This pilot suggests an initiative to evaluate and enhance the social appropriateness of AI-powered conversational agents, particularly focusing on scenarios where cultural, gender, religious and ethnic factors may introduce unwanted biases. This pilot centers on developing a virtual advisory agent capable of providing guidance in sensitive domains such as career counseling and university program recommendations, where biased responses could have significant real-world consequences. The fundamental challenge lies in ensuring that the agent can navigate complex social interactions while maintaining awareness of cultural practices and social norms. This requires drawing upon theoretical frameworks that recognize social order as being embedded within shared structures of knowledge and cultural values.

The pilot employs innovative methodologies including prompt engineering and bias stimulation strategies to systematically uncover potential biases in AI-generated conversations, utilizing both open datasets and synthetically generated dialogues based on diverse personas to reveal biases that might not emerge with real user samples. By combining social practices theory with advanced natural language processing techniques, this pilot aims to establish benchmarks and methodologies for quantitatively assessing the presence of social biases, unusual patterns and contextually inappropriate emotional content in AI-generated responses, ultimately contributing to the development of more socially aware and equitable language technologies.

The IP allows researchers to systematically evaluate how their conversational agent responds to culturally sensitive scenarios in career counseling and university recommendations. Through the IP, the team can input diverse prompts representing different cultural, gender, religious, and ethnic contexts to test the agent's responses. The platform enables them to experiment with various prompt engineering strategies and bias stimulation techniques using both open datasets and their synthetically generated personas, providing immediate feedback on whether the agent maintains appropriate social awareness across different demographic scenarios.

Furthermore, the IP integrates the pilot's technological components into a unified testing environment. This allows the respective researchers to continuously test and improve their quantitative bias assessment methodologies, provide retroactive feedback to the technical partners, which can iteratively refine their approaches based on real-world testing scenarios.

Pilot 3: “Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user’s goals, making API calls and respond with empathy” (D5.1, subsection 2.3)

This pilot focuses on developing and evaluating an advanced LLM-based virtual agent specifically designed for customer service applications across diverse industries including financial institutions, insurance companies and utility providers. The core innovation lies in creating a sophisticated agent that can be trained on enterprise-specific conversational datasets and then seamlessly generalize to new enterprises without requiring additional fine-tuning with company-specific data. The virtual agent is equipped with access to both structured and semi-structured enterprise documents, enabling it to retrieve and intelligently utilize relevant information when responding to complex customer inquiries.

The development process addresses several critical technical challenges, including the precise retrieval of factual information from vast databases, the creation of sophisticated algorithms to determine when API calls should be initiated, and the implementation of advanced natural language understanding with dialog-state tracking capabilities that can decipher indirect user responses through pragmatic reasoning. A particular emphasis is placed on ensuring high accuracy while preventing the dissemination of unverified information or hallucinations, and enabling the agent to accumulate and synthesize user intents across multiple dialog steps for coherent conversation flow. To achieve these objectives, the pilot leverages specialized training datasets that closely mimic real-world customer service conversations, incorporating authentic enterprise documentation to ensure the agent's retrieval mechanisms are trained on representative data that reflects the complex demands of modern customer service across various industries and scenarios.

Effectively, in this case, the IP is deployed as a centralized platform where the LLM-based agent can be iteratively refined and validated across different enterprise scenarios. Documents from financial institutions, insurance companies and utility providers can be uploaded to the IP and subsequently test how well the agent retrieves relevant information, handles complex inquiries, and responds without requiring extensive fine-tuning. The

platform provides the means to experiment with different prompts, dialogue flows and document retrieval scenarios while observing the agent's performance in real-time.

Additionally, the IP facilitates the critical technical challenges addressed in this pilot by offering a controlled environment where developers can test and refine the agent's API calling algorithms, natural language understanding capabilities and dialog-state tracking mechanisms. The platform enables systematic evaluation of the agent's ability to synthesize user intents across multi-turn conversations and maintain coherent dialogue flow across different industry contexts.

Pilot 4: “Upgrading support call centers through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues” (D5.1, subsection 2.4)

In this case, the objective is develop an LLM-powered supervision system for healthcare call centers that provide critical support to parents seeking advice about newborn care. The system is designed to handle initial communication with callers, assess the urgency level of their concerns, and collect essential information while they wait for human medical staff to become available. By managing both routine inquiries and emergency situations, the system will provide structured summaries and data to human operators, enabling more efficient handoffs and reducing the workload on junior medical staff who may lack experience handling complex cases with anxious callers providing incomplete information.

To support this development, the pilot will create a comprehensive multimodal audio corpus consisting of 150 simulated dialogues based on realistic scenarios. The data collection will involve natural speakers portraying callers while using both human speakers and text-to-speech technology for service provider responses. This corpus will include not only audio recordings and transcriptions, but also emotional context and structured ontologies categorizing inquiry types, ultimately serving as the foundation for recommendation systems that assist medical staff by suggesting solutions and relevant information while maintaining human oversight of all critical decisions.

The IP gives the capability to the pilot team to experiment with the language models and refine them using their specialized 150-dialogue corpus of parent-newborn care scenarios. Through the IP, developers will test how well the AI handles different types of urgent vs. routine inquiries, fine-tune the system's ability to extract key information from anxious callers, and customize the dialogue flows to match the specific medical protocols used by healthcare providers. The platform enables iterative testing of prompt engineering and context handling to ensure the LLMs can appropriately assess urgency levels and generate structured summaries that medical staff can quickly understand and act upon.

Additionally, medical staff will use the IP to test various scenarios, provide feedback on the recommendations and summaries, and help refine the system's responses to ensure they align with clinical best practices. This collaborative testing approach would be essential for building trust in the AI system among healthcare workers, while also allowing the development team to collect valuable feedback that could drive improvements to the underlying ELOQUENCE technologies for handling sensitive, high-stakes conversations in medical contexts.

From the quantitative perspective the IP will integrate (or alternatively support) the assessment methodologies and validation technologies necessary for satisfying the project's objectives as these are manifested through the respective Key Results (KRs) tied to the pilots. These KRs can be grouped in two categories:

- a. Comprehensive methodologies to evaluate conversational AI systems across diverse application scenarios (**KR11 through KR15**)
- b. Pilot demonstrations to validate ELOQUENCE technologies in real-world contexts (**KR16 through KR18**)

D5.1 contains the systematic presentation of the methodologies for achieving each KR, whereas detailed validation outcomes are to be reported in D5.4. A summary of these is presented next:

Table 1. Summary of pilot-related KRs

OBJ ID	Key Result	Target Metric	Validation Method
4	KR11	20% improvement in first call resolution for call center deployment	Baseline metrics and evaluation methodology (D5.1 subsection 3.3)
	KR12	100% increase in satisfaction feedback for call center deployment	Assessment tools and methodology (D5.1 subsection 3.5)
	KR13	50% improvement in customer satisfaction index	Comprehensive methodology (D5.1 subsection 3.5)
	KR14	20% improvement in call containment rates	Baseline establishment and metrics framework (D5.1 subsections 3.3 & 3.4)
	KR15	Safety-critical application metrics establishment	Domain-specific safety metrics (D5.1 subsections 3.1 to 3.4)
5	KR16	Demonstrate virtual agent capabilities in safety-critical call center scenarios	Validation results from Pilots 3 and 4
	KR17	Demonstrate virtual agent functionality in smart home environments	Validation results from Pilot 1
	KR18	Demonstrate socially aware virtual agents with bias evaluation capabilities	Validation results from Pilot 2

3 User Manual

3.1 UI overview

The **IP** interface is structured around a modular and task-oriented design, enabling users to interact efficiently with LLMs. It guides users through all key operations, from document ingestion and index creation to model interaction and performance evaluation by feedback — all within a unified environment.

The interface has functional areas that are accessible through a tab. They are aligned to the three primary stages of use:

- **Prepare knowledge sources** through document upload and embedding configuration
- **Engage with language models** through prompts, task configuration and parameter configuration
- **Review user feedback** on the quality and relevance of model outputs.

At the top of the interface, a navigation bar gives access to the **Playground**, **Ingestion**, and **Feedback** tabs. Each tab presents a clean, consistent layout with interactive widgets (e.g., dropdowns, buttons, input fields) that adapt based on the selected task configuration. Input modes include **text and audio**, depending on the capabilities of the chosen model and task.

Throughout the interface, users can:

- Select and switch between different **task configurations** (Basic LLM, RAG, Dialogue Manager, Audio).
- Choose your desired **LLM model** from the list.
- Configure **retrieval parameters** such as document index, chunk size and embedding method.
- Submit prompts and view model outputs in a structured conversation pane.
- Save, restore and download **conversation sessions** and **ingestion results**.
- Provide and review **qualitative feedback** using dedicated fields and download/export options.

Every element of the IP is designed to make working with generative AI and retrieval pipelines transparent, repeatable and adaptable. It supports both rapid experimentation and structured evaluation in applied settings.

3.1.1 Tabs and Layout

The IP's user interface is organized into three primary tabs: **Playground**, **Ingestion** and **Feedback**. This structure reflects the typical workflow of interacting with LLMs, enhanced with retrieval capabilities.

- The **Playground tab** is the central space for interacting with the system. Users can type or speak their questions, select a task configuration (e.g., Basic LLM, RAG, Dialogue Manager, Audio), and receive generated responses. The layout includes the conversation window, an input area, task-specific parameters, and controls to submit prompts or save session history. It is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The main playground tab

- The **Ingestion tab** is dedicated to preparing the knowledge base for retrieval tasks. In this section, users can upload documents, configure how they should be chunked and embedded, and store the results in a vector index. The interface includes fields for setting chunk size, selecting a splitting strategy, choosing an embedder and assigning an index name. The ingestion is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The ingestion tab

- The **Feedback tab** depicted in Figure 3 provides tools for reviewing user evaluations of model responses. It displays a table of feedback entries, including whether responses were marked as helpful, any custom comments, the model used, and the prompt context. Filtering options and a download button make extracting insights for analysis or model fine-tuning easy.

Figure 3. The feedback tab

Overall, the interface is designed to guide users through a clean and modular layout, from uploading and indexing documents to querying the system and analyzing its performance.

3.1.2 Concept of Tasks

The Interactive Playground interface is built around **task configurations**, which define how the system interprets user input and generates responses. A task determines the internal processing logic used during an interaction. Selecting the appropriate one is essential to obtaining meaningful results.

There are four primary task types available:

- **Basic LLM:** This is the simplest configuration. The user's input is sent directly to the LLM, which responds to the prompt without using or considering additional documents or references. This mode is best for open-ended questions and general use.
- **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG):** In this configuration, the system first searches a document index (vector store) for semantically relevant chunks of text. These retrieved passages are then passed along with the user's input to the LLM, enhancing the response with grounded information. This model is well-suited for factual, data-driven queries.
- **Dialogue Manager:** This task uses a pipeline that orchestrates multiple components — such as document retrieval, context handling and dialogue state tracking — to produce more conversational and structured interactions. It is instrumental when the system must follow multi-turn conversations or enforce specific dialogue logic.
- **Audio:** When a user selects the Audio task, the panel prompts him to create a voice message with his microphone, transcribe the verbal language to text, and then pass the text to the selected model. Using voice input, users can engage more naturally with improved accessibility and real-time input.

Each task type offers a different level of complexity and capability. Users must select a task before submitting input, and in some cases, task-specific settings (e.g., index name for RAG or vector store selection) must also be configured. The current task selection is reflected visually in the interface and can be changed at any time.

3.2 Vector Stores and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)

3.2.1 What is RAG?

RAG is a hybrid architecture that enhances the performance of LLMs by integrating external knowledge retrieval into the generation process. Instead of relying solely on the model's pre-trained parameters, RAG pipelines first use a retriever component—often based on vector similarity search—to fetch the most relevant documents or passages from an external knowledge base or vector database, such as those built with FAISS or LanceDB. These retrieved documents are then passed as context to a generative model (e.g., a transformer-based LLM like GPT or BERT variants), which uses the additional information to produce more accurate, grounded and context-aware responses. This approach is particularly useful in open-domain question answering, chatbots, and other NLP applications where up-to-date, domain-specific or verifiable knowledge is essential. RAG reduces hallucination, improves factual accuracy, and allows updating the system's knowledge without retraining the model, by simply updating the underlying document store.

3.2.2 Ingestion of Documents

Using this interface, a user can upload documents, break them into pieces that make sense to work with, and turn them into vectors that the system can use for searching or understanding content during a conversation. This is called ingestion, and it is an essential enabling factor for generating text using RAG. The ingestion screen is detailed in Figure 4.

Playground Ingestion Feedback

Index Name

Chunk length (char-based) Percentile thr (sem-based)

Splitting strategy

Vector Store

Embedder

Uploaded File(s)

Select file(s) to upload... Supported extensions [*.pdf, *.docx, *.csv, *.tsv, *.html, *.md, *.txt]

Run Ingestion

Figure 4. Details of the ingestion process

Playground Ingestion Feedback

Index Name

Chunk length (char-based) Percentile thr (sem-based)

Splitting strategy

Vector Store

Embedder

Uploaded File(s)

Select file(s) to upload... Supported extensions [*.pdf, *.docx, *.csv, *.tsv, *.html, *.md, *.txt]

Run Ingestion

Figure 5. Choosing the index name

Before starting the ingestion process, the user needs to choose a name for the index they are about to create. This name will act as a label for collecting uploaded and processed documents. Think of it like making a folder on your computer where all the transformed data will be stored.

This field is mandatory since the system needs a unique name to identify and retrieve this specific group of documents later. Once the ingestion is complete, the index will be saved in the selected vector store under this name. Later on, when the user is running queries in the Playground (especially with the RAG or Dialogue Manager task types), they will be able to specify this index name to ask the system:

“Search for relevant information in this specific collection.” The step is detailed in Figure 5.

Chunking Configuration

Before documents can be embedded, they must first be split into smaller parts called chunks. This is important because language models and embedding tools have limits on the amount of text they can process at once.

Chunking makes it possible to:

- Handle large documents (like PDFs with many pages)
- Improve retrieval accuracy by associating answers with smaller, more focused segments of text

- Optimize performance for embedding and searching
- The Chunking Configuration section allows users to control:
- How large each chunk should be (in characters)
 - Whether the split happens at arbitrary positions or meaningful places like sentence boundaries
 - Whether semantic information is used to guide the splitting

These settings ensure the chunks are just the right size and contextually useful for downstream retrieval. The respective part is highlighted in Figure 6.

The screenshot shows the 'Ingestion' configuration page. The 'Chunking Configuration' section is highlighted with a red box. It contains three input fields: 'Chunk length (char-based)' with a value of 500, 'Percentile thr (sem-based)' with a value of 95, and 'Splitting strategy' with three radio buttons: 'By Length (simple)', 'By Length (recursive)' (which is selected and highlighted in yellow), and 'Semantic'. Below this section are fields for 'Vector Store' (set to 'BSC-public'), 'Embedder' (with three options: 'sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2', 'sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2', and 'text-embedding-ada-002'), and 'Uploaded File(s)'. At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Select file(s) to upload...' and 'Run Ingestion', along with supported file extensions: [*.pdf, *.docx, *.csv, *.tsv, *.html, *.md, *.txt].

Figure 6. Ingestion process chunking configuration

The following parameters allow fine control over this process:

- **Chunk length (character-based):** defines the maximum number of characters allowed in each chunk. A typical value is 500 characters. Setting this value too low may result in fragmented, less meaningful chunks, while setting it too high could lead to oversized chunks that may be truncated or ignored by the embedding model. The default setting generally provides a good balance for most documents.
- **Percentile threshold (semantic-based):** is a value that becomes relevant when using advanced chunking methods such as semantic or recursive splitting. It determines how semantically distinct two parts of the text must be to be split. For example, a threshold of 95 tells the system only to split when there is a significant shift in meaning, helping to preserve the coherence of concepts across paragraphs.
- **Splitting strategy:** controls the method used to divide the text. The available strategies are:
 - **By-length (simple):** This option splits the document into fixed-length character blocks without considering sentence or paragraph boundaries. It is the fastest option, but it may cut off sentences midway.
 - **By-length (recursive):** Tries to respect natural text boundaries (such as sentence endings or paragraph breaks) while obeying the chunk length limit. This option offers a better trade-off between accuracy and speed.
 - **Semantic:** The most intelligent method splits text based on semantic similarity. It detects natural topic transitions and creates chunks accordingly. This approach produces high-quality chunks but may require more processing time.

Selecting the appropriate configuration depends on the type of content being ingested. Short documents or structured data may perform well with simple splitting. In contrast, longer or more complex texts — such as technical reports or narrative content — benefit greatly from recursive or semantic strategies.

Vector Store Selection

The screenshot shows a configuration interface with the following sections:

- Index Name:** A text input field.
- Chunk length (char-based):** A dropdown menu set to 500.
- Percentile thr (sem-based):** A dropdown menu set to 95.
- Splitting strategy:** Three buttons: 'By-Length (simple)', 'By-Length (recursive)' (highlighted in yellow), and 'Semantic'.
- Vector Store:** A dropdown menu with 'BSC-public' selected, highlighted by a red box.
- Embedder:** Three buttons: 'sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2', 'sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2', and 'text-embedding-ada-002'.
- Uploaded File(s):** A text input field.
- Buttons:** 'Select file(s) to upload...' and 'Run Ingestion'.
- Text:** 'Supported extensions [*.pdf, *.docx, *.csv, *.tsv, *.html, *.md, *.txt]'.

Figure 7. Selecting a vector store

A vector store is a collection of documents transformed into semantic vectors. Instead of storing plain text, the system stores numerical representations that capture the meaning of each passage.

This enables the system to retrieve meaning-based information rather than rely solely on literal keyword matching. For example, if a document says, “The sun provides solar energy,” and the user asks, “How is sunlight used as power?”, the system can recognize the semantic similarity and retrieve the relevant passage.

Each ingestion operation creates a new index within a selected vector store.

The Vector Store Selection option allows the user to choose the target vector store where the new index will be created. It is highlighted in Figure 7.

Embedder Selection

The screenshot shows a configuration interface with the following sections:

- Index Name:** A text input field.
- Chunk length (char-based):** A dropdown menu set to 500.
- Percentile thr (sem-based):** A dropdown menu set to 95.
- Splitting strategy:** Three buttons: 'By-Length (simple)', 'By-Length (recursive)' (highlighted in yellow), and 'Semantic'.
- Vector Store:** A dropdown menu with 'BSC-public' selected.
- Embedder:** Three buttons: 'sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2', 'sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2', and 'text-embedding-ada-002', highlighted by a red box.
- Uploaded File(s):** A text input field.
- Buttons:** 'Select file(s) to upload...' and 'Run Ingestion'.
- Text:** 'Supported extensions [*.pdf, *.docx, *.csv, *.tsv, *.html, *.md, *.txt]'.

Figure 8. Selecting a vector store

The user must choose which embedding model to use during the ingestion process. The embedder is the component that transforms each chunk of text into a numerical vector, a mathematical representation of its semantic meaning. The system stores these vectors and uses them later to retrieve the most relevant content based on user queries.

Several embedding models are available, each with different trade-offs in terms of speed, accuracy and resource requirements. You can see the details in section 3.3.3.

Choosing the right embedder depends on the nature of the content and the desired accuracy. MiniLM is often sufficient for fast prototyping or general use. For more demanding use cases, especially those involving critical search tasks or large-scale document retrieval, MPNet or Ada-002 are more suitable. The embedder selection is depicted in Figure 8.

Uploading Files and Running the Ingestion Process

Figure 9. Uploading documents for ingestion

As part of the ingestion workflow, the user must upload one or more documents to be analyzed and transformed into vector representations. This step is essential for enabling semantic retrieval later on, particularly in configurations like RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) or Dialogue Manager, where the system enriches its responses by retrieving relevant information from a pre-processed knowledge base.

To begin, the user clicks on the "Select file(s) to upload..." button, which opens a file picker, allowing the selection of one or more documents from the local device. The selected files are then listed in the Uploaded File(s) area, confirming they are ready to be processed. The system supports a variety of widely used formats, including .pdf (PDF documents), .docx (Microsoft Word), .csv and .tsv (spreadsheet files), .html (web pages), .md (Markdown), and .txt (plain text). This flexibility makes it easy to ingest structured reports, user manuals, technical documentation and even website content.

Once the user has configured all necessary parameters — such as the index name, chunking strategy, vector store and embedding model — the ingestion process can be started by clicking the "Run Ingestion" button. At this point, the system begins processing the uploaded documents through a multi-step pipeline: first, it splits the content into manageable chunks according to the chosen strategy and size settings; then, each chunk is passed through the selected embedder to generate a vector, capturing the semantic meaning of the text excerpt. Finally, all generated vectors are saved into the selected vector store under the index name defined by the user.

Once the process is complete, the new index is immediately available for use within the Playground interface. For queries using RAG or Dialogue Manager tasks, this index can be referenced to retrieve relevant information in the response. The document upload and ingestion process are highlighted in Figure 9.

3.2.3 Private vs. Public Vector Stores

The use of vector stores for RAG poses a challenge for data confidentiality. Since all the pieces of documents must be stored in the vector store, we need to ensure that sensitive data is handled with care.

For this reason, we introduce the concept of a private vector store: an instance hosted within a private network that communicates with the IP to deliver only the necessary data snippets on demand. Populating the private vector store is also possible in this configuration.

Figure 10. Comparison of public vs private vector store setup

In the private setup, the partner runs an instance of a vector store wrapped as a web server locally. This vector store web server is exposed, so users employing the IP can use it seamlessly for both creating the vector store and retrieving the snippets. The data is stored locally, but travel over the internet back and forth. There is also the option to run this in a hybrid regime, so the user would be responsible for populating the vector store with data locally, and Playground would use it only for runtime retrieval. We compare the approaches in Figure 10. Furthermore, the data flows in respective variants are illustrated in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11. Data flow of retrieval when using the public vector store

Figure 12. The data flow of retrieval in the private setup

3.3 Served Models

The models are served in the BSC cluster in an on-demand manner. This means that not all the supported models are available all the time; some are only available upon request. The exact procedure for providing access to the requested model has yet to be determined. Currently, it's handled using requests to the BSC team. This aspect will be managed during the execution of task 5.4.

3.3.1 LLMs

GPT-3.5 (OpenAI)

- **Developer:** OpenAI
- **Architecture:** Transformer-based, part of the GPT-3 family
- **Release Date:** March 2023
- **Supported Languages:** Primarily optimized for English. Demonstrates proficiency in multiple languages, including Spanish, French, German, Chinese and others
- **Key Features:**
 - Enhanced reasoning and code generation capabilities compared to GPT-3
 - Supports a 16K token context window
 - Powers ChatGPT's free tier and API services

Salamandra

- **Developer:** European research consortium led by BSC and IULA
- **Architecture:** Decoder-only transformer models with 2B, 7B, and 40B parameters
- **Release Date:** February 2025
- **Supported Languages:** 35 European languages with focus on English, Catalan and Spanish
- **Key Features:**
 - Trained from scratch on multilingual data covering 35 European languages and code

- Includes instruction-tuned variants for chat applications
- Open-source under Apache 2.0 license, with publicly available training and evaluation scripts

OLMo 2 (Allen Institute for AI)

- **Developer:** Allen Institute for AI (AI2)
- **Architecture:** Dense autoregressive transformer models with 7B and 13B parameters
- **Release Date:** January 2025
- **Supported Languages:** Primarily English
- **Key Features:**
 - Introduces "Dolmino Mix 1124" data mixture for improved downstream task performance
 - Incorporates instruction tuning with reinforcement learning using verifiable rewards (RLVR)
 - Fully open-source, including training data, code and intermediate checkpoints

EuroLLM-9B (EuroLLM Team)

- **Developer:** EuroLLM Team
- **Architecture:** Decoder-only transformer with 9 billion parameters
- **Release Date:** September 2024
- **Supported Languages:** All 24 official EU languages + Additional languages including Arabic, Catalan, Chinese, Hindi, Japanese, Korean or Russian
- **Key Features:**
 - Designed for multilingual capabilities across all official EU languages and additional relevant languages
 - Trained on a diverse, high-quality multilingual dataset
 - Open-weight model, promoting transparency and accessibility
 - Demonstrates strong performance on multilingual benchmarks and machine translation tasks
 - Part of the EuroLLM initiative to advance open, multilingual language models for Europe

3.3.2 Audio Models

Qwen2-Audio (Alibaba)

- **Developer:** Alibaba Cloud
- **Architecture:** Multimodal transformer integrating audio and text inputs
- **Release Date:** July 2024
- **Supported Languages:** Chinese (Mandarin), Cantonese, English, French, Italian, Spanish, German, Japanese
- **Key Features:**
 - Processes various audio inputs (e.g., speech, music, environmental sounds)
 - Supports two modes: voice chat and audio analysis
 - Utilizes natural language prompts for diverse audio tasks
 - Outperforms previous models like Gemini-1.5-pro in audio-centric instruction-following tasks

3.3.3 Embedding models

[sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2](#)

This model is a lightweight and efficient embedding model suitable for most general-purpose applications. It balances performance and speed well, making it ideal for small to medium-sized datasets or environments with limited computational resources.

[sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2](#)

This model provides more accurate and nuanced semantic embeddings than MiniLM. It is recommended for higher precision in semantic search or when working with complex or technical documents. However, it requires slightly more computation time.

3.4 User Feedback Collection

Figure 13. Display of the user feedback

The **Feedback tab** provides an organized overview of user experiences, showing how the system performed during interactions. It is mainly for gathering qualitative and quantitative feedback about the generated outputs' relevance, quality and clarity. This tab is particularly valuable for system developers, trainers or evaluators who want to understand how well the model performs in real-world use cases.

The central part of this tab is a table where each row represents a single instance of feedback submitted by a user. The table includes the following columns:

- **User** – The username or email address of the person who submitted the feedback.
- **Feedback** – A boolean value (True/False) indicating whether the user found the system's response helpful.
- **Custom_feedback** – Any additional comments provided by the user in free text (e.g., "nice answer!", "too concise").
- **Model** – The name of the language model used for the response (e.g., GPT-3.5-turbo, Qwen2-Audio).
- **System_prompt** – The prompt or system instruction used for the interaction (if any was set).
- **Retrieved** – Text excerpts from the retrieval system (if the task involved document search, such as in RAG or Dialogue Manager mode).

Users can apply filters at the top of the tab to inspect feedback by specific columns (e.g., filter only False ratings or a particular model). This allows for focused analysis, such as checking only the responses marked as unhelpful for a specific model.

Finally, a "**Download feedback**" button lets users export all visible feedback entries as a JSON file. This is useful for offline analysis, training data preparation or tracking model improvements over time. The feedback display and download screen is shown in Figure 13.

3.5 Advanced Functionality

3.5.1 System Prompts

This section of the interface provides tools to define custom prompts, manage session history and perform batch processing using structured data files. It is divided into three functional groups:

Prompt Management

- **System Prompt:** allows users to define a global instruction that influences the behavior of the language model. Example: "You are an expert technical assistant. Respond concisely."
- **Prompt:** a dropdown list where saved prompts can be selected for reuse.
- **Save prompt:** this function stores the current **System Prompt** and **Prompt** fields as a reusable preset. Once saved, it appears in the dropdown list.

3.5.2 Storing Conversation Sessions

This area manages past conversations by saving and restoring entire sessions.

- **History (dropdown):** lists previously saved sessions for selection.
- **Load history:** loads a saved conversation into the chat interface, restoring user inputs and model responses. This enables the user to **resume a previous session** or review past queries and answers.
- **Download History:** exports the conversation into a **JSON file**, including all user requests and corresponding system responses.

When history is downloaded, the exported `.json` file follows the structure shown in Figure 14.

```
{
  "history": [
    ["hi", "This is a Dialogue Manager response to 'hi'. This is retrieved from [1]"],
    ["What is the goal of Eloquence?", "This is a Dialogue Manager response to..."],
    ...
  ],
  "prompt": "",
  "name": "2025-04-23-..."
}
```

Figure 14. Structure of the downloaded history snapshot

- Each item in the "history" array is a pair: [`<user_input>`, `<model_response>`].
- The "name" field typically contains a timestamp or a unique identifier for the session.

3.5.3 Batch Data Processing

This functionality allows uploading a file containing **multiple user inputs**, which are then processed in a single run.

- **Upload & run from data:** This option opens a file selector, allowing users to upload a `.json` file containing structured input for **batch execution**. The system processes each item sequentially using the current task and LLM settings.

File structure:

```
{  
  "Conv_1": ["User 1.1", "User 1.2"],  
  "Conv_2": ["User 2.1", "User 2.2"],  
}
```

- **Download processed data:** Once processing is complete, the user can export the results (responses, retrieved documents or any associated metadata). This is useful for post-processing, auditing, or integrating the outputs into reports.

4 Architecture and Technical Documentation

4.1 Architecture overview

Figure 15. Overall architecture of the Interactive Playground system

The architecture is designed in a modular way as depicted in Figure 15. Our implementations are wrapped in virtual containers running on the same machine to ensure fast communication. To achieve modularity, the expected means of communication is via API.

The user communicates with the service exclusively through one entry point using a secure connection protocol (i.e. *HTTPS*). The LLMs are hosted in different nodes equipped with GPUs and we use fast inference toolkits like *vLLM*. The communication with LLMs is performed exclusively via the internal BSC network.

4.1.1 Containerization

Each service runs in a virtualized environment, implemented using Docker containers. Below we provide a description of individual services:

Interactive Playground Frontend

Location: BSC virtual exposed node

This is the main container exposed on a public address that runs a web server to handle user requests. It serves the API and provides the user with the UI. It is connected to all other services, and therefore, it is considered an entry point that orchestrates the whole system.

Retriever

Location: BSC virtual exposed node/partner local network

The retriever container hosts a slim web server that can serve requests to create/update the vector stores and return retrieved results. It is a default part of the system running on BSC, however, it can be also hosted locally in a private network and the Playground can be configured to use it.

Hosted model

Location: BSC GPU cluster node

A running container running third-party code with the vLLM server, providing fast inference with LLMs.

Dialogue Manager

Location: BSC virtual exposed node

Since it is strictly related to the realization of the Pilots, its implementation within the IP is currently on-going and will be completed during Task 5.4. However, its integration has already been considered in the definition of the IP architecture. This component is supposed to provide a service with more complex decision processes, involving NLU and policy decisions. It will be connected to the Playground and use the same user interface.

4.1.2 Audio Processing

The audio is updated either using a streaming interface, in which the client application sends 200ms chunks periodically, or by sending a whole audio recording at once. The user interface now uses the streaming version and API for the batch (whole recording version). In the final version, the API will support both options. For more API details, see Appendix A.

Upon uploading, the audio is converted into standard WAV (PCM) format and then encoded to conform to the input format expected by each model.

4.1.3 Vector Store Integration

The vector store is handled by a retriever service, described in section 5.1.1 The API endpoints aren't meant to be used directly; however, the functionality is corresponding to API endpoints /ingest, /retrieval and /list_vs described in section 4.

The Playground is configured to connect to a certain retriever service as described in section 5.2.

Each vector store is created using a specific embedding model. To ensure consistency, the same embedding model must be used when retrieving from that vector store. This requirement is automatically handled by the retriever service.

4.2 System Configuration

The configuration files are in configurations/ directory. These are simple JSON files that can be edited when preparing the docker image.

4.2.1 Task configs

Location

`configurations/task_configs/*.json`

File structure

```
{  
  "name": "RAG", # name of the task  
  "RAG": true, # if retrieval should be used  
  "interface": "text", # what is the interface for input? text/audio
```

```
"service": "local" # local is default, for remote services like a Dialogue manager, one can use remote-  
http://address:port  
}
```

This file describes a task config that is handled by the Playground. We can select different combinations of features to handle the workflows.

4.2.2 Retrievers

Location

`configurations/retrievers.json`

File structure

```
{  
"BSC-public": "http://127.0.0.1:7999"  
}
```

Configures the address to which the retriever instance can be reached.

4.2.3 User Configuration

Location

`/path/to/user/workspaces/username/retrievers.json`

File structure

```
{  
"partner-local": "http://address:port"  
}
```

User-specific retriever instance hosted locally. Can achieve more secure handling of sensitive data.

4.3 Running the instance

4.3.1 Run the IP

To run an IP instance, we need to clone the repository from

<https://github.com/ELOQUENCEAI/eloquence-interactive-playground>

Next, we have to build the Docker image:

```
docker build -t eloquence-interactive-playground
```

Subsequently, we can run the container as follows:

```
docker run -d --net="host" -v /path/to/persistent/folder:/data eloquence-interactive-playground
```

Here, we provide a path to persistent data folder that is used to keep the user data and vector stores.

Environment Variables

When running the image, we can provide several environment variables, specifically:

```
ENV PERSISTENT_DATA="/data" # path to persistent data root inside the container; need to correspond to  
mapped volume used in docker run
```



```
ENV RETRIEVER_ENDPOINT="http://127.0.0.1:7999" # an address on which we can reach the instance of retriever handling the vector store
```

```
ENV AVAILABLE_LLMS='["http://localhost:8082/v1,salamandra-7b-instruct,Salamandra (MN5)"]' # list of available LLMs in format address:port,model_id,model_name
```

Configuration files

The configuration files are located in PERSISTENT_DATA/configurations, For more details refer to section 4.2.

4.3.2 Run the local Vector Store

The running container needs a mounted volume to be able to store the indexes permanently. First, let's create a dedicated directory for this purpose.

mkdir persistent_data_root

The latest version of the image can be pulled from Docker Hub using the command:

```
docker pull vhidecekomilia/eloquence-local-vs:latest
```

This prepared image has a port exposed on 8030.

Alternatively, the image can be built manually using a standard Dockerfile, where the exposed port for external communication must be explicitly specified.

```
docker build -t eloquence-local-vs --build-arg EXPOSED_PORT=8030 -f Dockerfile-local-vs .
```

Once we have the image and the persistent directory, we can run the container with:

```
docker run -d -v persistent_data_root:/data eloquence-local-vs
```

Depending on the networking setting, the argument `--net=host` may also be needed in order to be able to connect to the container.

Now, the container is running a web server which is bind to "[http://localhost:\\${EXPOSED_PORT}](http://localhost:${EXPOSED_PORT})".

You should make sure that the incoming internet traffic is forwarded to this port.

4.4 Used Software

We use multiple third-party software libraries to achieve the smooth functioning of the whole Playground. Below we describe the most important ones briefly.

Docker

Docker is an open-source platform that enables developers to automate the deployment of applications inside lightweight, portable containers. Containers package an application with all its dependencies, ensuring it runs consistently across different environments. Docker simplifies development, testing, and deployment workflows, making it easier to build scalable and reproducible software systems. We use it to create individual images and run the respective containers.

Gradio

Popular framework to implement user interfaces to ML models. Uses a client-server architecture that allows for the efficient implementation of frontend features and connection with server-side code.

LanceDB

LanceDB is a high-performance, open-source vector database optimized for machine learning and AI workloads. It uses the Lance format, a columnar data format designed for fast, versioned and efficient storage of both vector and structured data. LanceDB integrates easily with popular frameworks like PyTorch and Hugging Face, enabling

seamless end-to-end workflows for building and querying AI-powered applications. We use this to implement the vector store build and the retrieval operation.

FastAPI

FastAPI is a modern, high-performance web framework for building APIs with Python based on standard Python type hints. It provides automatic data validation and asynchronous support for high concurrency. Designed for speed and developer productivity, FastAPI is ideal for building RESTful APIs and microservices.

vLLM

High-throughput and memory-efficient inference engine for LLMs, designed to maximize performance on modern hardware. It introduces PagedAttention, an optimized attention algorithm that enables faster and more efficient batched inference. Built for scalability and ease of integration, vLLM supports popular models like LLaMA, GPT and others with minimal code changes. vLLM is used in our system to host the LLMs on the BSC cluster.

5 Future Work

5.1 Planned features/modules

We are planning to enhance the IP implementation with a range of additional features and improvements aimed at increasing both functionality and interoperability within the broader Eloquence framework. Below we outline the key directions for future work:

Implement model compatibility checks to ensure the correct usage of models for their intended modalities—for example, preventing the accidental combination of audio-based and text-based models in incompatible tasks. This will improve system robustness and user guidance.

Enable streaming audio support via the REST API, allowing for real-time processing and interaction with audio data. This is particularly relevant for conversational or multimodal use cases that require low-latency processing.

Extending support to additional audio and embedding models, broadening the applicability of the platform and making it more adaptable to different pilot requirements and data modalities.

Integrate tools and modules developed within other Work Packages (WPs) of the Eloquence project, with the aim of building a cohesive ecosystem where different components can interoperate seamlessly. This includes aligning interfaces, data formats, and model outputs to ensure consistency across modules.

Prepare the IP implementation for deployment in pilot scenarios, by tailoring it to real-world constraints and workflows identified in pilot planning. This includes ensuring scalability, robustness, and usability in environments reflective of actual use cases.

Support end-to-end integration and orchestration of multimodal processing pipelines, which will be essential for demonstrating the full capabilities of the Eloquence platform in practical settings.

These enhancements are designed not only to improve the technical performance of the IP implementation but also to position it as a central component in the overall architecture of the Eloquence project, contributing directly to its successful validation through pilots.

6 Appendix A: API References

Content example Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

This section outlines the available PI requests. For each endpoint, we provide detailed documentation, including example requests and corresponding responses.

POST /query - Send request to the LLM

Initiates a language model query with custom parameters and optional audio input.

Endpoint

POST /query

Content-Type: multipart/form-data

Form Fields

Field	Type	Required	Description
body	string (JSON)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JSON-encoded payload describing the LLM query
audio	file (optional)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Optional audio file input

Body Schema

```

history: List[List[str]]
input_text: str
llm_name: str
task_config: Optional[str] = "Basic"
docs_k: Optional[int]
temp: Optional[float]
top_p: Optional[float]
max_tokens: Optional[int]
index_name: Optional[str]
retriever_address: Optional[str] = "public"
system_prompt: Optional[str] = None

```

Example request

```

import requests
import json

```

```
url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/query"
```

```
body_data = {  
    "history": [["Hi", "Hello!"], ["How are you?", "I am fine."]],  
    "input_text": "Tell me a joke.",  
    "llm_name": "gpt-3.5-turbo",  
    "task_config": "Basic",  
    "docs_k": 5,  
    "temp": 0.7,  
    "top_p": 0.9,  
    "max_tokens": 100,  
    "index_name": "Eloquence",  
    "retriever_address": "public",  
    "system_prompt": "You are a helpful assistant."  
}
```

```
# if you want to send input to audio model
```

```
files = {  
    "audio": open("path/to/audio.wav", "rb")  
}
```

```
data = {  
    "body": json.dumps(body_data)  
}
```

```
response = requests.post(url, data=data, files=files)  
print(response.json())
```

Example Response

```
{  
    "text": "Why couldn't the bicycle stand up by itself? It was two tired!"  
    "documents":["Doc content 1", "Doc content 2", ...]  
}
```

POST /batch_query - Send batch request to the LLM

Processes a set of data input as a JSON file, makes requests to the specified LLMs and return the whole conversation histories.

Endpoint

POST /batch_query

Content-Type: multipart/form-data

Form Fields

Field	Type	Required	Description
body	string (JSON)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JSON-encoded payload describing the LLM query
content_file	file	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JSON file with data to be processed

Body Schema

llm_name: **str**

task_config: **Optional[str]** = "Basic LLM"

docs_k: **Optional[int]**

temp: **Optional[float]**

top_p: **Optional[float]**

max_tokens: **Optional[int]**

index_name: **Optional[str]**

retriever_address: **Optional[str]** = "public"

system_prompt: **Optional[str]** = None

Example request

```
import requests
import json

url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/batch_query"

body_data = {
    "llm_name": "gpt-3.5-turbo",
    "task_config": "Basic",
    "docs_k": 5,
    "temp": 0.7,
    "top_p": 0.9,
    "max_tokens": 100,
```

```
"index_name": "Eloquence",  
"retriever_address": "public",  
"system_prompt": "You are a helpful assistant."  
}
```

if you want to send input to audio model

```
"""
```

File structure:

```
{  
    "Conv_1": ["User 1.1", "User 1.2"],  
    "Conv_2": ["User 2.1", "User 2.2"],  
}
```

```
"""
```

```
files = {  
    "data_file": open("path/to/batch_data.json", "rt")  
}
```

```
data = {  
    "body": json.dumps(body_data)  
}
```

```
response = requests.post(url, data=data, files=files)
```

```
print(response.json())
```

Example Response

```
{  
    "processed": {  
        "Conv_1": [["User 1.1", "Response 1.1"], ["User 1.2", "Response 1.2"]],  
        "Conv_2": ...  
    }  
}
```

POST /ingest- Create and update an index

Uploads a file and metadata for ingestion into an index for retrieval. If the index doesn't exist, it's created.

Endpoint

POST /ingest

Content-Type: multipart/form-data

Field	Type	Required	Description
body	string (JSON)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JSON-encoded metadata for document ingestion
file	file	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The document to ingest (e.g., .pdf, .txt)

Body Schema

```
index_name: str
embed_name: str
chunk_size: Optional[int] = 500
percentile: Optional[float] = 0.9
splitting_strategy: Optional[str] = "recursive"
retriever_address: Optional[str] = "public"
```

Example request

```
import requests
import json

url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/ingest"

body_data = {
    "index_name": "my-index",
    "embed_name": "sentence-transformer",
    "chunk_size": 512,
    "percentile": 0.95,
    "splitting_strategy": "recursive",
    "retriever_address": "public"
}

files = {
    "file": open("path/to/document.pdf", "rb")
}

data = {
    "body": json.dumps(body_data)
```

```
}
```

```
response = requests.post(url, data=data, files=files)
```

Example Response

```
{  
    "status": "success",  
    "msg": "Document ingested successfully"  
}
```

GET /retrieval – Retrieve similar documents

Uses specified retriever and index to retrieve documents that are relevant to the submitted query.

Endpoint

GET /retrieval

Body Schema

retriever_address: Optional[str] = "public"

query: str

index_name: str

top_k: Optional[int] = 5

Example request

```
import requests  
import json  
  
url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/retrieval"  
  
params = {  
    "index_name": "my-index",  
    "query": "this is a query",  
    "retriever_address": "public",  
    "top_k": 5  
}  
response = requests.get(url, params=params)
```

Example Response

```
{  
    "available": ["Doc text 1", "Doc text 2", ...]
```

```
}
```

GET /feedback – Download user feedback

Downloads the user feedback, optionally filtered according to constraints.

Endpoint

GET /feedback

Body Schema

```
filter_column: Optional[str] = None
```

```
filter_value: Optional[str] = None
```

Example request

```
import requests
import json

url = "https://eloquence.it.bsc.es/feedback"

params = {
    "filter_column": "model",
    "filter_value": "gpt"
}
response = requests.get(url, params=params)
```

Example Response

```
{
    "filter": "model='gpt'",
    "feedback": [...]
}
```

GET /list_vs – List available vector stores

Sends the list of available indexes in the specified retrieve.

Endpoint

GET /list_vs

Body Schema

```
retriever_address: Optional[str] = "public"
```

Example request

```
import requests
```

```
import json

url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/list_vs"

params = {
    "retriever_address": "public",
}

response = requests.get(url, params=params)
```

Example Response

```
{
    "available": ["index 1", "index 2", ...]
}
```

GET /list_llms – list available LLMs

Sends the list of LLMs that are currently available to query.

Endpoint

GET /list_llms

Example request

```
import requests
import json

url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/list_llm"

response = requests.get(url)
```

Example Response

```
{
    "available": ["gpt", "Qwen2", ...]
}
```

GET /list_embedders – list of supported embedding models

Sends the list of available indexes in the specified retrieve.

Endpoint

GET /list_embedders

Example request

```
import requests
import json

url = "https://eloquence.lt.bsc.es/list_embedders"

response = requests.get(url)
```

Example Response

```
{
  "available": ["miniLM", ...]
}
```


Funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

UK Research
and Innovation